

Quality of fish oil-based dietary supplements available on the Italian market as related to the global fatty acid composition

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Abstract

The food supplement market is growing rapidly around the world and Italy ranks first in Europe in the consumption of food supplements with fish oil supplements representing a good part of such consumption. Conversely there are few papers about the quality control of fish oil supplements and none of them refer to the Italian market. In the present work, an analytical control about fatty acids in fish oil capsules purchased on the Italian market has been carried out. All products were essentially in compliance with the label declaration, with minor deviations. However, one product (the cheapest one) was of low quality as regards the global fatty acid composition which showed a high content of saturated fatty acids, a low content of polyunsaturated fatty acids and a low content of Omega-3 fatty acids. Method reliability has been particularly taken care of, with the total amount of fatty acids determined experimentally by saponification followed by gas chromatography - mass spectrometry.

1. Introduction

It is widely recognized that fish consumption prevents cardiovascular diseases and acts positively against other important pathologies. This is due to the composition of fatty acids rich in Omega-3, also known as n-3 fatty acids or n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (n-3 LC-PUFA) with Eicosapentaenoic (EPA) and Docosahexaenoic (DHA) as the major representatives. The amount of EPA + DHA consumed in the diet is considered of primary importance in preventing coronary heart disease (Mozaffarian & Rimm, 2006).

Food supplements fish oil-based had a growing market in recent years because they are expected to have the same beneficial effects as fish consumption. In USA the Omega-3 market is projected to grow at a CAGR (Compound Annual Growth Rate) of 13.1% to reach USD 8.52 billion by 2025 from 4.07 billion in 2019 (MarketsAndMarkets, 2019). At the global level the Omega-3 supplement market size was valued at USD 33.04 billion in the year 2016 (Grand View Research, 2017).

Despite this great turnover, scientific works aimed at controlling the quality of these products are scarce as already mentioned by Srigley and Rader (2014). As far as we know, data exists only for the markets of five countries in the world: Poland (Kolanowski, 2010) USA (Chee et al., 1990; Srigley and Rader, 2014) New Zealand (Bannenberg et al., 2017) Brazil (Galuch et al., 2018) and Finland (Damerau, 2020). Italy is the leading consumer of food supplements in Europe with a market share of 23% and a turnover of 3.3 billion Euros in 2018 (CENSIS, 2019). As regards fish oil supplements, in the year 2016 four million packs of Omega-3 supplements were purchased in Italy, for a total cost of 84 million euros (Il Fatto Alimentare, 2019). Recently a dietary supplement label database, FoodEx2 coding-based, was developed for supplements available on the Italian market: a total of 558 products have been entered into the database (Durazzo et al., 2020).

No scientific works exist in the literature about quality control of Omega-3 supplements from the Italian market. Such controls are to be deemed important. Galuch et al. (2018) in their study of the Brazilian market cite that two brands were discovered with addition of large amounts of soybean oil, which indicates product adulteration so leading the final consumers to ingest this low-cost oil believing that they are consuming adequate doses of EPA and DHA. Srigley and Rader (2014) found that contents of EPA and DHA met their respective label declarations in about 80% of the products examined, while Bannenberg et al. (2017) observed that the product compliance with the label was of 91%. In the present work an analytical control of fish oil supplements from the Italian market was carried out for the first time. As a further novelty it is highlighted that the agreement with the label may not be the only parameter that defines the quality of an Omega-3 supplement. It is always advisable to perform the study of the global fatty acid composition since in some cases it could be evidenced that a supplement which complies with the label may still be of poor quality.

2. Materials and methods

Three Omega-3 supplements of the most popular brands were purchased from retailers. All products are registered with the Italian Ministry of Health according to the law in force. Four capsules for each brand were opened and approximately 10 mg of the pooled oil were methyl derivatized. Derivatization was carried out with BF₃ methanol solution 14% and methanol (1:1) followed by extraction with n-hexane, as reported by Navigato et al. (2012). Individual analytical standards of fatty acids were purchased as methyl esters either from Merck KGaA[®] or from Larodan[®] (Solna, Sweden). After the purchase, the pure FA standards were dissolved in n-hexane and stored at a temperature of -30°C by using the Certan[®] capillary bottles, i.e. vials specially designed for optimum storage available from Merck KGaA[®].

An aliquot of oil from each brand was used to derive the total quantity of fatty acids per 100 mg of oil. To such aim it was used the Kinsella method (Kinsella et al., 1977). Briefly said about 100 mg of oil were subjected to saponification by means of 10% alcoholic KOH, the nonsaponifiable material was extracted with n-hexane and the residual soaps were acidified to pH 1.5. The free fatty acids were extracted with n-hexane, dried in a tared vial and the weight of fatty acids was determined. Total FAs as mg/100 mg oil for each one of the three supplements are shown in Table 1. As reported by Kinsella “these data are used to calculate the weights of individual fatty acids separated by gas chromatography” consistently with the areas of each peak. Such procedure was carried out in the present work after that the fatty acid response factors were adequately checked according to the European Union Regulation No 2568/91 (1991). The analytical quality control was performed by analyzing the Test Material “fish oil” from fapas[®], Sand Hutton, UK.

2.1 Instrumental analysis

Instrument used was a Varian 3900 gas chromatograph connected to the Mass Spectrometer Saturn 2100T (GC-MS) equipped with an Ion Trap analyzer. Injections were made in split mode (15:1) with an injection volume of 1 μ L. Injections showed excellent repeatability as evidenced by the syringe internal standard used (15:1 n5). Capillary column installed was a CP-WAX 52 CB (60 m \times 0.32 mm I.D., 0.50 μ m film thickness) from Chrompack[®], the Netherlands. Mass spectra were obtained in EI (Electron Ionization) mode at 70 eV. Ion trap temperature was 180°C. The selected Mass to Charge Ratio to acquire was in the 40-440 m/z range. Analyses were carried out in full scan mode.

GC-MS chromatograms were accurately reprocessed by performing a peak-by-peak identification and integration until the signal to noise ratio of 3.

For the 27 major FAs (Table 1) of which they were purchased the pure standards the identification was achieved by multiple confirmation criteria, mainly the coincidence of mass spectrum and retention time with the mass spectrum and retention time of the pure analytical standard injected in the same conditions. The check with the mass spectrum NIST[®] database completed the identification. The limit of detection was 0.005 mg FA / 100 mg oil. Figure 1 shows the GC-MS chromatograms of the three supplements analyzed.

Figure 1. GC-MS chromatograms of the three supplements analyzed. Chromatograms are overlaid

For all the other peaks (for which pure standards were not available) the objective was to assign or not their belonging to the fatty acid class. This operation turned out to be quite simple with the study of the mass spectrum. An example is shown in Figure 2 where it is reported, enlarged, the chromatogram area of Figure 1 between 24 and 33 min. In such zone a peak is visible between the fatty acid 14:0 and the fatty acid 15:0, but none of the standards available matches the retention time of this peak.

Figure 2. Magnification of Figure 1 in the area between 24 and 33 min

In Figure 3 it is reported the mass spectrum of the peak at about 30 min compared with the mass spectrum of the fatty acid 15:0 (supplement n.3).

Figure 3. On the left: mass spectrum of the unknown peak at 30 min in Figure 2; on the right: mass spectrum of the peak at 32 min in Figure 2 (fatty acid 15:0). Supplement n.3

It is evident the close similarity of the two spectra. As can be seen the molecular weight is 256 amu and it is clear that the spectrum on the left corresponds to a methylated fatty acid with 15 Carbon atoms without double C-C bonds. The signal 213 m/z corresponds to the loss of a propyl group in the ionization step. It is very likely that the peak at 30 min in Figure 2 refers to a C15 branched fatty

acid and in fact its mass spectrum fits very well with the one of methyl-9-methyltetradecanoate present in the NIST[®] mass spectrum database. In any case, the assignment of the peak to the fatty acid class is certain.

By studying the mass spectra, a total number of about 50 different fatty acids were detected in each sample, 27 of which were exactly identified, while the others were unambiguously assigned to the class of fatty acids.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the fatty acid composition of the three supplements analyzed. The values in the last row (total FAs) were experimentally obtained by the Kinsella method (section 2, materials and methods). Values for the individual FAs were derived from GC-MS chromatograms. In the supplement n.1 they were detected a total of 46 FAs while in the supplements n.2 and n.3 they were detected 55 and 47 FAs, respectively.

Twenty-seven fatty acids represented most of the total being 85% in the supplement n.1, 86% in the supplement n.2 and 91% in the supplement n.3. These 27 FAs, from Lauric to DHA, are listed in the first column of Table 1.

Table 1. Fatty acid composition of the three omega-3 supplements analyzed (mg/100 mg oil)

Fatty acids	Supplement n.1 (total n. of FAs detected: 46)	Supplement n.2 (total n. of FAs detected: 55)	Supplement n.3 (total n. of FAs detected: 47)
C12:0 (Lauric)	n.d.	n.d.	0.14
C13:0 (Tridecanoic)	n.d.	n.d.	0.03
C14:0 (Myristic)	0.05	0.13	6.29
C14:1 n-5 (Myristoleic)	n.d.	n.d.	0.05
C15:0 (Pentadecanoic)	0.01	0.06	0.54
C16:0 (Palmitic)	0.16	1.32	13.80
C16:1 n-7 (Palmitoleic)	0.11	0.44	7.71
C16:2 n-4 (Palmitolinoleic)	n.d.	0.08	1.21
C17:0 (Margaric)	0.06	0.10	0.35
C18:0 (Stearic)	2.94	4.27	2.77
C18:1 n-9 (Oleic)	2.87	6.17	9.55
C18:1 n-7 (Vaccenic)	1.29	2.48	2.72
C18:2 n-6 (Linoleic)	0.52	1.33	0.99
C19:0 (Nonadecanoic)	0.39	0.52	0.37
C18:3 n-3 (α -Linolenic or ALA)	0.34	0.70	0.72
C18:4 n-3 (Stearidonic)	0.47	1.54	2.75
C20:0 (Arachidic)	0.93	1.02	0.38
C20:1 n-11 (Gadoleic)	0.73	0.26	n.d.
C20:1 n-9 (Gondoic)	3.58	1.61	0.93
C20:2 n-6 (Dihomolinoleic)	0.39	0.13	n.d.
C20:4 n-6 (Arachidonic)	2.56	1.59	0.78
C20:4 n-3 (Omega-3 Arachidonic)	1.58	1.32	0.69
C20:5 n-3 (Eicosapentaenoic or EPA)	32.41	25.76	16.68
C22:1 n-11 (Cetoleic)	2.60	1.42	n.d.
C22:1 n-9 (Erucic)	0.18	0.44	n.d.
C22:5 n-3 (Docosapentaenoic)	2.71	2.91	1.37
C22:6 n-3 (Docosahexaenoic or DHA)	19.68	20.06	12.89
EPA+DHA	52.09	45.82	29.57
Σ n-3	57.19	52.29	35.10
Σ n-6	3.47	3.05	1.77
Σ n-6/ Σ n-3 (dimensionless value)	0.06	0.06	0.05
Σ saturated fatty acids (SFA)	4.54	7.42	24.67
Σ monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA)	11.36	12.82	20.96
Σ polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA)	60.66	55.42	38.08
Other fatty acids	13.58	12.07	8.72
Sum (total FAs)	90.14	87.73	92.43

n.d.: not detected

Compliance with the label was as follows (mg/100 mg oil):

Supplement n.1 - EPA label value: 40, EPA measured value: 32.41 (81%); DHA label value: 20, DHA measured value: 19.68 (98%).

Supplement n.2 - EPA label value: 33, EPA measured value: 25.76 (78%); DHA label value: 22, DHA measured value: 20.06 (91%).

Supplement n.3 - EPA label value: 15, EPA measured value: 16.68 (111%); DHA label value: 10, DHA measured value: 12.89 (129%).

It may be noted that in supplements n.1 and n. 2 EPA is about 80% of what was declared on the label: also Chee et al. (1990) in their study of marine oil capsules measured about 80% of labeled content as regards EPA. In a work on Omega-3 fatty acid dietary supplements by the US Department of Agriculture Dietary Supplement Ingredient Database Team it was observed a statistically significantly difference between the measured and the label level of EPA, being the measured level lower than the declared one (USDA, 2015).

The other measured values (DHA in all supplements, EPA in supplement n.3) are essentially in agreement with the label being the supplement 3 slightly in excess of what declared but this does not necessarily mean a higher quality, as exposed below. Rather in some cases ingredients may be added by producers in amounts exceeding the label claims in order to compensate for losses during shelf life (USDA, 2015).

By considering the 27 main fatty acids, the ratio $\Sigma n-6/\Sigma n-3$ is equal to 0.06, 0.06 and 0.05 for supplement n.1, n.2 and n.3 respectively. These values are well in compliance with the current guidelines which recommend not to exceed the value of 1 in the diet for the ratio $\Sigma n-6/\Sigma n-3$. Such values were to be expected for products derived from fish oil which are in fact used also to rebalance the diet.

As regards the distribution between saturated fatty acids (SFA), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) a noticeable difference can be observed between the supplement n.3 and the other two. The series $\Sigma SFA-\Sigma MUFA-\Sigma PUFA$ as mg/100 mg oil is equal

to 4.54 - 11.36 - 60.66 (5-11-61) for supplement n.1, 7.42 - 12.82 - 55.42 (7-13-55) for supplement n.2 and 24.67 - 20.96 - 38.08 (25-21-38) for supplement n.3. This indicates that an effective purification step has been carried out for supplements n.1 and n.2 in order to eliminate the less valuable saturated fatty acids, in fact the values for 1 and 2 are not typical of fish oil, while the values for supplement n.3 are (Nevigato et al., 2012).

In this respect it can be considered, for example, the value of 16:0 (Palmitic) that is generally one of the most concentrated fatty acids in fish oils. In supplements n.1 and 2 16:0 is instead one of the less concentrated FAs (0.16 and 1.32 mg/100 mg oil) while in the supplement n.3 it is one of the most concentrated (13.80 mg/100 mg oil). A similar situation can be observed for 14:0.

Furthermore the two saturated FAs 12:0 and 13:0 are not detectable in supplement 1 and 2. On the contrary they are present in supplement 3 even if in low quantity (the same low quantity generally observed in fish oils). It must be emphasized that the production of good omega-3 supplements involves accurate purification steps by means of which free fatty acids, heavy metals, colored compounds, contaminants and other impurities are removed from raw fish oil, making the oil much purer. Generally, the Short Path Distillation technique is used which is also named Molecular Distillation, a special type of very high vacuum distillation. The technique also allows the concentration of fish oils which leads to a higher total Omega-3 content and a higher concentration of EPA and DHA (Rossi et al., 2012; Olli et al., 2013). A fractionation step may be used to remove saturated fatty acids. Supplement n.3 appears to have undergone incomplete purification process. In addition to the significant presence of saturated fatty acids, supplement no. 3 has in fact a total Omega-3 content of only 35 mg /100 mg oil compared to 57 and 52 mg/100 mg oil of supplements 1 and 2 respectively.

For EPA and DHA there is a noticeable difference between the supplement n.3 and the other two. The EPA content in n.3 is half of n.1 and two thirds of n.2, while the DHA content in n.3 is two thirds of n.1 and n.2. In terms of percentages the sum EPA+DHA represents 58 and 51% of total fatty acids in supplements n.1 and 2, while in supplement n.3 is 33%. This forces the consumer to

take more oil from supplement n.3 to obtain the same quantity of bioactive molecules with possible side effects, such as, for example, the intake of contaminants in non-negligible quantities if the product was not perfectly purified.

4. Conclusions

Three fish oil supplements of the most popular brands from Italian market were analyzed. Apart from a slight difference between the measured and declared content of EPA, supplements n.1 and 2 have a higher quality than the supplement n.3, the cheapest one. This last in fact has a higher content of saturated fatty acids thus suggesting that it has undergone an incomplete purification. Furthermore, the lower content of Omega-3 in supplement n.3 may force the consumer to take more oil, with possible side effects. This indicates that the compliance with the labeled content of EPA and DHA is not the only parameter to be investigated when fish oil supplements are analyzed. Rather, an analysis of the overall composition of fatty acids is much more useful. The next necessary step of the present study is a wider campaign of measures with the analysis of a higher number of samples, of different type also (algae oil for example) to check to which extent these preliminary conclusions may be extended to the Italian market of Omega-3 supplements, that was never investigated until now.

References

- Bannenberg, G., Mallon, C., Edwards, H., Yeadon, D., Yan, K., Johnson, H., Ismail, A. (2017). Omega-3 Long-Chain Polyunsaturated Fatty Acid Content and Oxidation State of Fish Oil Supplements in New Zealand. *Scientific Reports*, 7, Article number 1488.
- CENSIS, Centro Studi Investimenti Sociali, Rome (Italy) 2019. Salute: gli integratori alimentari utilizzati da 32 milioni di italiani. <https://www.censis.it/welfare-e-salute/salute-gli-integratori-alimentari-utilizzati-da-32-milioni-di-italiani> (accessed 01-12-2020).
- Chee, K.M., Gong, J.X., Good Rees, D.M., Meydanl, M., Ausman, L., Johnson, J., Siguel, E.N., Schaefer, E.J. (1990). Fatty acid content of marine oil capsules. *Lipids*, 25, 523-528.
- Damerou, A., Ahonen, E., Kortensniemi, M., Pukanen, A., Tarvainen, M., Linderborg, K.M. (2020). Evaluation of the composition and oxidative status of omega-3 fatty acid supplements on the Finnish market using NMR and SPME-GC-MS in comparison with conventional methods. *Food Chemistry*, 330, Article number 127194.
- Durazzo, A., Camilli, E., D'Addezio, L., Piccinelli, R., Mantur-Vierendeel, A., Marletta, L., Finglas, P., Turrini, A., Sette, S. (2020). Development of dietary supplement label database in Italy: Focus of foodEx2 coding. *Nutrients*, 12, Article number 89.
- European Union Regulation, Commission regulation (EEC) No 2568/91 (1991) Analysis by gas chromatography of methyl esters of fatty acids: use of correction factors. Official Newspaper of the European Community 1991R2568:59-60.
- Galuch, M.B., Carbonera, F., Magon, T.F.S., Da Silveira, R., Dos Santos, P.D.S., Pizzo, J.S., Santos, O.O., Visentainer, J.V. (2018). Quality assessment of omega-3 supplements available in the brazilian market. *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*, 29, 631-638.
- Grand View Research (2017). Omega 3 Supplement market size, share & trends analysis report by source (fish oil, krill oil), by application (infant formula, food & beverages, nutritional supplements, pharmaceutical), and segment forecasts, 2018 - 2025. <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/omega-3-supplement-market> (accessed 01-12-2020).
- Il Fatto Alimentare (2019). Gli integratori di omega 3 servono davvero? Secondo i primi dati di uno studio decennale sembrerebbe di no. <https://ilfattoalimentare.it/integratori-omega-3-servono.html> (accessed 01-12-2020).
- Kinsella, J.E., Shimp, J.L., Mai, J., Weihrauch, J. (1977). Fatty acid content and composition of freshwater finfish. *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society*, 54, 424-429
- Kolanowski, W. (2010). Omega-3 LC PUFA contents and oxidative stability of encapsulated fish oil dietary supplements. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 13, 498-511.
- MarketsAndMarkets (2019). Omega-3 Market by Type (DHA, EPA, and ALA), Application (Dietary Supplements, Functional Foods & Beverages, Pharmaceuticals, Infant Formula, and Pet Food & Feed), Source (Marine and Plant), and Region - Global Forecasts to 2025. <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/omega-3-omega-6-227.html> (accessed 01-12-2020).

- Mozaffarian, D., & Rimm, E.B. (2006). Fish Intake, Contaminants, and Human Health Evaluating the Risks and the Benefits. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 296, 1885-1899.
- Navigato, T., Masci, M., Orban, E., Di Lena, G., Casini, I., Caproni, R. (2012). Analysis of fatty acids in 12 Mediterranean fish species: Advantages and limitations of a new GC-FID/GC-MS based technique. *Lipids*, 47, 741-753.
- Olli, J.J., Breivik, H., Thorstad, O. (2013). Removal of persistent organic pollutants in fish oils using short-path distillation with a working fluid. *Chemosphere*, 92, 273-278.
- Rossi, P., Grosso, N.R., Pramparo, M.C., Nepote, V. (2012). Fractionation and concentration of omega-3 by molecular distillation. In Bradley, T.G., & Vargas F.P. *Eicosapentaenoic acid: Sources, health effects and role in disease prevention* (pp. 177-203). New York, NY, USA: Nova Science Publishers, Inc.
- Srigley, C.T., & Rader, J.I. (2014). Content and composition of fatty acids in marine oil omega-3 supplements. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 62, 7268-7278.
- USDA, US Department of Agriculture, National Institute of Health, Methods and Application of Food Composition Laboratory. Dietary Supplement Ingredient Database Release 4.0 (DSID4). Omega-3 Fatty Acid Dietary Supplement Study. Research Summary. March 2015 (August 2017, Minor Revisions). <https://dietarysupplementdatabase.usda.nih.gov/Omega3.php> (accessed 01-12-2020)

Figure 1. GC-MS chromatograms of the three supplements analyzed. Chromatograms are overlaid

Figure 2. Magnification of Figure 1 in the area between 24 and 33 min

Figure 3. On the left: mass spectrum of the unknown peak at 30 min in Figure 2; on the right: mass spectrum of the peak at 32 min in Figure 2 (fatty acid 15:0). Supplement n.3

